

A Theory of Colour on the Basis of Molecular Strain. Part VI.—Effect of Sulphur on Colour.

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In a series of papers from this laboratory (Tewari and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 161 ; 1927, 4, 201 ; 1928, 5, 59) the effect of nitrogen on colour has been studied at length, and in that connection it was thought that it would be interesting to find out what effect an atom of sulphur has on the colour of organic dyestuffs.

It is well-known that thiopyronine in which an atom of sulphur has replaced the pyrone oxygen atom of Pyronine G is much deeper in colour than the latter. Similarly Purvis, Jones and Tasker, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2287) have shown that the thio-oxalates are deeper in colour than the corresponding oxalates which are by themselves colourless. Dutt and Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1939, 2414) also have shown that many mercaptan derivatives of azo-dyes and thio-fluorescein are deeper in colour than the corresponding dyes containing oxygen in place of sulphur. This conclusion is borne out by the recent researches of Reid and his collaborators (Reid, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1936, 1926 ; 1926, 48, 19, 528).

In all the above cases where sulphur replaces an oxygen atom it produces an increase of colour probably because of the fact that though, like oxygen, it is divalent and potentially quadrivalent it has got much greater atomic weight and necessarily its loading effect is more intense. Therefore it will be expected that when a sulphur atom replaces a carbon atom a similar intensification of colour will take place. An interesting case for verification of such an expectation would be to prepare a series of pyronine dyestuffs from thio-diglycollic acid (I).

and compare them with the corresponding dyestuffs derived from glutaric acid (II), a number of which has already been described by Dutt and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 123, 2524 ; Dutt, *ibid.*, 1926, 129, 1132).

The dyestuffs described in this paper have a deeper colour than the corresponding dyes of the glutaric acid series. Further quantitative work regarding this is being done in this laboratory.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiodiglycollic Acid.—Chloroacetic acid (95 g.) was added little by little to a solution of sodium carbonate (145 g.) dissolved in the minimum quantity of water. Caustic soda (45 g.) was next dissolved in about a 100 c.c. water and the solution was divided in two parts, one of which was saturated with sulphuretted hydrogen gas and the two halves were simultaneously added with constant stirring to the solution of sodium chloroacetate. The whole mass becomes pasty. It is left as such for about two to three hours. Next concentrated sulphuric acid (100 gm) is added carefully and the hot solution is filtered and left overnight, crude thiodiglycollic acid separates which is filtered off and recrystallised from water, m. p. 129°.

Resorcinolthiodiglycollein.—Thiodiglycollic acid (3 g.) was mixed with resorcin (4.4 g.) and the mixture was heated to a temperature of about 150° and kept at that temperature. A few drops of sulphuric acid were used as a condensing agent. When the viscous mass became solid it was powdered and treated with hot water. Then it was dissolved in caustic soda and filtered and the dye precipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid. It was filtered and washed thoroughly and redissolved in caustic soda and precipitated again by dilute acetic acid. It does not melt up to 310° and dissolves in alcohol. In alkaline solutions it shows a yellow colour with a green fluorescence. (Found S, 9.46. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5S$ requires S, 16.01 per cent.).

Phloroglucinolthiodiglycollein.—Thiodiglycollic acid (3 g.) and phloroglucinol (4.4 g.) were heated together at 170°-180° for 6 hours, few drops of sulphuric acid being added as a condensing agent. The solid mass was thoroughly powdered and extracted by means of caustic soda solution and filtered. The dye was precipitated by

dilute hydrochloric acid. It dissolves in many of the organic solvents. In caustic alkali it shows an orange colour. It could not be crystallised. (Found: S, 9.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_7S$ requires S, 9.2 per cent.).

Phenolthiodiglycollein.—Thiodiglycollic acid (5 g.) was mixed with phenol (4.2 g.) and tin tetrachloride (5 g.) and heated for about 8 hours at 110° - 120° . The viscous melt was next treated with dilute ammonia and filtered. The filtrate was treated with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated dye was collected could not be crystallised from alcohol, acetic acid, and chloroform. Brown powder dissolving in alkalis with deep red colour, m. p. 129° . (Found: S, 11.02. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4S$ requires S, 10.6 per cent.).

4:4-Tetraethyl-diamino-2:2-amidophenylthiodiglycollein.—Thiodiglycollic acid (3 g.) and *m*-diethylamidophenol (3 g.) were heated with a few drops of sulphuric acid for about 6 hours at 130° - 140° . The tarry mass was next dissolved in hydrochloric acid and filtered. The dye was precipitated by a cold dilute solution of sodium carbonate. The dye was obtained as a dull pink amorphous powder which could not be crystallised, m. p. 172° - 173° . (Found: S, 7.2. $C_{24}H_{30}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 7.5 per cent.).

4:4-Diamino-2:2-aminophenylthiodiglycollein.—Thiodiglycollic acid (3.8 g.) was heated with *m*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (8 g.) to a temperature of about 220° and kept at that temperature for about an hour. The hard mass on cooling was powdered and refluxed with absolute alcohol. It was filtered and the filtrate reduced to a small bulk and filtered again from the solid residue that was deposited. The filtrate was then treated with water. The dye separates as pale yellow powder, dissolving in alcohol with an yellow colour having green fluorescence. It melts at 241° . (Found: S, 9.9. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3O_2S$ requires S, 10.2 per cent.).

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